

Data Management Plan Information

La Chouffe DMP New

This DMP has been created for managing data representatives within the Open Publishing domain in the context of the [Open Science](#) exam at the University of Bologna. Starting from our research questions related to scientometric studies, we aim for data about academic articles and to understand how much aggregators (in our case, the Directory of Open Access Journals, [DOAJ](#), and [Crossref](#)) present shared information.

The DOAJ acts as an umbrella organisation aiming to increase Open Access journals' visibility. They have an [API](#) and a [public data dump](#) with the information about both articles from their journals and journals themselves.

Crossref is an organisation that aims to improve scientific communication; they have aggregated huge quantities of articles' metadata and, for some, their reference lists. In this context, we used their [REST API](#).

Our research involves the articles from Open Access journals in DOAJ and their data on Crossref. The produced datasets will be created by manipulating both datasets.

The datasets, methods used to gather them and further information will be available on Github (as a reference, [here is the Github repository](#)).

DOI of the protocol describing the methodology used in our research:
10.17504/protocols.io.kxygz7yww8j/v5

DOI of the software used for creating these datasets: 10.5281/zenodo.6857310

DOI of the datasets: 10.5281/zenodo.6562909

DOI of the article of our research: 10.5281/zenodo.6570290

Funder

None

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none

Organisations

Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna

Researchers

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Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)

Datasets

Title: DOAJ and Crossref populated DATASET

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset contains the data from articles in [DOAJ](#) organised in journals' ISSN and with the data gathered from [Crossref's API](#).

In particular, it will contain:

1. ISSN of the journal;
2. DOI of the article;
3. Publication Year of the article;
4. Presence of article in [Crossref](#);
5. Presence of reference list in Crossref;
6. Articles in the reference list, with DOI if present;
7. Entity responsible for the assertion of reference's DOI

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- This dataset is an intermediate dataset, to which we will add information.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

• reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

- Data will be gathered from dumps made available by [DOAJ](#) and from [Crossref's API](#)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files, Numerical
- The file will be in .json format.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- GB (gigabyte)
- The whole, uncompressed dataset is of size over 20 GB, we also made a compressed version of it, weighting 1.9 GB

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry
- This data can be useful to both replicate the study or to gather new insights on the world of Open Access publication.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
- Dublin Core
- We will describe the data by following Dublin Core . This is a well known standard that ensures flexibility. Data.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes
- To describe the dataset, we used DCat standard vocabulary as we want the description to be appropriate for this kind of resource .

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
- The metadata will be freely available on zenodo and have their own DOI.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
- The metadata will be hosted on Zenodo. It will be in Turtle/RDF format.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

- <https://libguides.princeton.edu/c.php?g=102546&p=930626>
- Princeton - YYYYMMDD_NAME

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow the Semantic Versioning standard for naming the dataset

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - Yes, we will use DOIs provided by Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- No
 - The metadata will be contained in Zenodo.

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will use json, an open format.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 -

One can use many different open source softwares to access json files. As an example, Sublime Text.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- No
 - We will not use personal data, nor any data that could be reconducted to real people. Some of our data refers to established scientific journals, which identities might be inferred. We do not share, however sensible data about the journals as well, besides of publication year, subject field, and country, which are already available to the public in their original repositories.

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - We will make the data openly accessible and downloadable.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- Zenodo
 - We will make the data available through Zenodo or other online repositories if the data is too large.

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery
 - We will consider hosting a backup on our local disk.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

- No
 - The data will be available for download from [Zenodo](#)

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

- Yes
 - [DCat](#) and [DublinCore](#)

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
- The data will be readily accessible by the end of the project, if not earlier.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

We will use [CC0 v.1.0](#)

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
- We will make data available for anyone to access and reuse; anyone can contact us if support is needed.

Examples of possible usage of this data might be found on protocols.io at dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygz7yvv8j/v3

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3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure, Other
- Zenodo will be the main access point to our described data

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
- All three people are in charge of the creation and quality of the data.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Supervision and Best Practices

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Software and Data Production

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Supervision and Best Practices

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive
 - We will publish the data on open repositories. If a migration will be needed, we will consider asking for support to Zenodo.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: DOAJ cleaned articles DATASET

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset will be created by combining the dump retrieved from DOAJ, removing the unnecessary information, for it to be updated with the data from Crossref. In particular, it will contain:

1. DOI of the article
2. ISSN(s) associated with the article

3. Year of creation of the article

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To combine with other data
 - This data will be used in combination with data retrieved from Crossref's API, and additional information from DOAJ's journals dump.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

• reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

- The data will be secondary data, curated by DOAJ; we just cleaned it.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files, Numerical

- The dataset will contain:

DOIs (Direct Object Identifier) about each article contained in DOAJ. A [DOI](#) is a unique identifier for an article, software, a DMP...

ISSN (International Standard Serial Number): a unique identifier for a periodical publication.

Year of publication.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- MB (megabyte)
 - The whole JSON file for the articles in DOAJ weighs about 20 GB. Our cleaned dataset weighs 796 MB, with a significant size reduction; the zipped version weighs 93 MB.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry

- This data could be reused by researchers interested in the context of Open Science, or to better evaluate the contributions of Open Access articles to the academic world, maybe combining it with other sources or going the other way around (from [Crossref](#) to [DOAJ](#), using these articles). Moreover, it can be used to verify how rigorous our analysis was.

The choice of the [CCO](#) license follows this idea as well.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
- Dublin Core
 - We will describe the data by following Dublin Core. This is a well-known standard that ensures flexibility.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes
 - To describe the dataset, we used [DCAT](#) standard vocabulary as we want the description to be appropriate for this kind of resource.

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
-

The metadata will be freely available on [Zenodo](#) and have its own DOI.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be freely harvestable from [Zenodo](#). It will be in Turtle/RDF format.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

- <https://libguides.princeton.edu/c.php?g=102546&p=930626>

- Princeton - YYYYMMDD_NAME

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow the [Semantic Versioning](#) standard for naming the dataset

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - We will use DOIs provided by Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- No
 - The metadata will be contained in Zenodo.

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will use JSON, an open format easy to reuse.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - One can use many different open source software to access JSON files. As an example, Sublime Text.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- No
 - We will not use personal data, nor any data that could be reconducted to real people. Some of our data refer to established scientific journals, from which identities might be inferred. We do not share, however sensible data about the journals as well, besides publication year, that is already available to the public in their original repositories.

DOAJ's original dump is registered under a CC0 license

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - We will make the data openly accessible and downloadable.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- Zenodo
 - DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6562909

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery
 - We will consider hosting a backup on our local disk.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

- No
 - The data will be available for download from Zenodo

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

- Yes
 - [DCat](#) and [DublinCore](#)

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
 - The data will be readily accessible by the end of the project, if not earlier.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

[CC0 v.1.0](#)

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes

- We will make data available for anyone to access and reuse; anyone can contact us if support is needed.

Examples of possible usage of this data might be found on protocols.io at dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygz7yvv8j/v3

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3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Other
 - Zenodo will be the main access points to our described data

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- No
 - All three people will be responsible for the production of software and data.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Supervision of processes, Best practices

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Supervision of processes, Best practices

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Responsible for Software and Production of Data

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive
 - We will publish the data on open repositories. If a migration will be needed, we will consider asking for support from Zenodo.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on insecure, unmanaged storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: La Chouffe SOFTWARE

Template: Horizon 2020

This software will be used to enrich our datasets, by first cleaning the [DOAJ](#) dataset, then connecting to the [API of Crossref](#) and ultimately extracting knowledge from those passages.

It will be coded in [Python](#) programming language.

First, it outputs a JSON file and finally a pickled CSV file for performing statistical analysis on it.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information, To share information, To develop a product
 - This is software developed to perform scientometric analyses on our [DOAJ](#) and [Crossref](#) data. It will be divided into components aimed at managing different stages of the manipulation and comparing the data obtained.

Namely:

main.py
batches_cleaner.py
journals_cleaner.py
multithread_populating.py
populator.py
NotebookViz.ipynb

It will be developed using the [Python](#) programming language and its libraries.

All of these will be listed in the dedicated repo. The development of those scripts can also be found in the [Open Science](#) repositories under the team [La Chouffe, on protocols.io](#), and [Zenodo](#).

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- Other
 - The data will be the scripts employed in creating the other two datasets, cleaning them, and performing analysis on them.
- Code

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Software
 - Scripts programmed in Python and a Jupyter Notebook.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- MB (megabyte)
 - It is reasonable to expect that the software size will be at most 1 MB.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Industry
 - This data can be useful to both replicate the study and gather new insights into the world of Open Access publication.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

- Yes
 - To compare and combine with other data, To develop new products/ services

2.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

a.

Pandas Python Library - <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

b.

Plotly - <https://plotly.com/>

c.

tqdm - <https://tqdm.github.io/>

d.

country_converter - <https://pypi.org/project/country-converter/>

e.

pycountry_converter - <https://pypi.org/project/pycountry-convert/>

f.

doimmanager - ??? <https://github.com/opencitations/index/blob/master/index/identifier/identifiermanager.py> DA CAMBIARE

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
 - Dublin Core
 - We provided a metadata description of the software using [Dublin Core Terms](#) and [OntoSoft](#)

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes
 -

We used [OntoSoft](#) as it provides a vocabulary for describing software.

- Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

We will make the metadata about our software freely available.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

We will host all our metadata on Zenodo.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow [Semantic Versioning](#) to maintain a rigorous development of our software.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - We will use DOIs provided by Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- No
 - We will provide it in containers such as Zenodo.

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will create .py and .ipynb files.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - Any text editor can be used to open .py files e.g. Sublime Text

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - The data will be accessible on Github and on Zenodo.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub
 - The data will be hosted in a repository in Github, in particular in the global [Open Science](#) repository, as well as on Github.

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery
 - We will have our scripts on Github and in local repositories.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

- at end of project
 - The software, as well as the data, are available.

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
 - The data will be available during development and, globally, by the end of the project.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

MIT License

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
 - We will provide support to any future users. If support is needed, one can open a Github issue, contact us or refer to the protocol, we published with this study

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Other
- Github, Zenodo

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
 - Two people are tasked with maintaining the software, while the third acts as an overseer.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Software Development and Data Gathering

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Software Development and Data Gathering

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Software Development and Data Gathering

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other, Personal Archive
- Hosted on Github
 - Data reuse will be assured by using personal storage as well as hosting on Github.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: DOAJ and Crossref aggregated DATASET

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset aggregates information retrieved both from Crossref and Doaj, also introducing information useful to further statistical analysis.

In particular, it will contain for each row:

ISSN: ISSN (or ISSNs) of the journal

DOI: Digital Object Identifier of the article

Doi Number (1): used for counting the number of articles

On Crossref (1, 0): used for counting the number of articles on Crossref (indicating the presence on Crossref)

Reference (1,0): used for counts (indicating the presence of reference lists)

Reference Number: total number of references in the reference list

Asserted by Publisher: number of references identified by the publisher

Asserted by Crossref: number of references identified by Crossref

Reference Undefined: number of articles in the reference list without a DOI

Year: Year of publication of the article

Country: Country of origin of the Journal

Subject: Main Subject of the Journal (Following the LCC classification)

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information, To share information, To develop a product
 - This dataset contains the final information needed for answering the main research question of our study, i.e. How do publishers behave when asserting metadata of DOAJ journals on Crossref?

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?
reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?
Text files, Numerical

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?
Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- MB (megabyte)
 - We pickled the final data frame into a file of weight 632 MB.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry
 - This data can be useful to both replicate the study or to gather new insights on the world of Open Access publication.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
 - Dublin Core
 - We will describe the data by following [Dublin Core](#). This is a well known standard that ensures flexibility.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- Yes
 - To describe the dataset, we used [DCAT](#) standard vocabulary as we want the description to be appropriate for this kind of resource.

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be freely available on Zenodo.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be hosted on Zenodo. It will be in Turtle/RDF format.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.8 Please provide more details and examples on used naming conversions

- <https://libguides.princeton.edu/c.php?g=102546&p=930626>
- Princeton - YYYYMMDD_NAME

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow the [Semantic Versioning](#) standard for naming the dataset

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - Yes, we will use DOIs provided by [Zenodo](#).

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- No
 - The metadata will be contained in [Zenodo](#).

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

No

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will use pickle, a Python-specific open format.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - To use this file, you need to use Python, which is open source. It is possible to unpickle it using the pickle or the pandas module.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

No

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- No
 - We will not use personal data, nor any data that could be reconducted to real people. Some of our data refer to established scientific journals, from which identities might be inferred. We do not share, however sensible data about the journals as well, besides publication year, subject field, and country, which are already available to the public in their original repositories.

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - We will make the data openly accessible and downloadable.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- Zenodo

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery
 - We will consider hosting a backup on our local disk.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

- No
 - The dataset is freely downloadable from Zenodo.

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

- Yes
 - [DCat](#) and [DublinCore](#)

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
 - The data will be readily accessible by the end of the project, if not earlier.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

Since part of the data used here comes from the [DOAJ Journal Dump](#), we used the [CC-BY-SA-4.0](#) license for this part of the dataset.

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

No

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
 - We will make data available for anyone to access and reuse; anyone can contact us if support is needed.

Examples of possible usage of this data might be found on protocols.io at dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.kxygz7yww8j/v3

[not last version yet]

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure, Other
 - Zenodo will be the main access points to our described data

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
 - All three people are in charge for the creation and quality of the data.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Software and Data Production

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Software and Data Production

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Supervision and Best Practices

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive
 - We will publish the data on open repositories. If a migration will be needed, we will consider asking for support to Zenodo.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No